

EBFMC25-OP-71 · Evaluation of the Impact of Education Provided in a Family Health Center on Attitudes Towards Early Diagnosis of Cervical Cancer

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cancers are increasing worldwide and are the 2nd most common cause of death. The 4th most common cancer in women is cervical cancer. In Turkey, cervical cancer ranks 10th among female cancers. The incidence of cervical cancer has more than halved since the mid-1970s with the widespread use of screening. The aim of this study was to determine how women's attitudes towards early diagnosis of cervical cancer changed after information training on cervical cancer by a primary care physician.

Material and Methods: The study was an educational intervention study with a one-group pretest-posttest design. The population of the study consisted of 670 women aged 30-65 years registered to Tirebolu Family Health Center (FHC) numbered 28.15.002. With G*PowerVersion 3.1.7 program, a sample size of at least 54 patients was calculated to represent the population. Face-to-face education about cervical cancer was given to 54 participants. Pre- and post-training evaluation was performed with the questionnaire form created by the researchers and the “Attitude Scale for Early Diagnosis of Cervical Cancer”. Data were analyzed with IBM SPSS V23.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 45.73 ± 8.98 years and most of the participants were housewives (72.7%). Although the rate of those who were aware of cervical cancer screening tests was quite high (96.4%), only 12.7% of the participants had received training on cervical cancer before. The mean total score of the women before the training was 100.76 ± 11.23 and the mean total score after the training was 102.47 ± 12.36 ($p=0.121$). The pre-training perceived sensitivity score was 29.20 ± 5.22 and the post-training perceived sensitivity score was 30.78 ± 6.67 ($p=0.012$). The pre-training perceived severity score was 27.09 ± 4.85 and the post-training perceived severity score was 26.38 ± 6.00 ($p=0.101$). The pre-training perceived barriers score was 21.00 ± 4.11 and the post-training perceived barriers score was 21.45 ± 4.51 ($p=0.346$), while the pre-training perceived benefits score was 23.27 ± 3.09 and the post-training perceived benefits score was 23.84 ± 3.93 ($p=0.065$).

Conclusion: An education program for cervical cancer screening should include cultural knowledge and communication skills. Health workers should provide opportunities for patients to provide women with adequate information and opportunities for screening tests. Since primary care is a place that patients can easily reach, healthcare professionals should be aware that they can provide the best service that patients can get from primary care and that patients are open to education and guidance. It is clear that with education, patients' awareness will increase and participation rates in screening will increase.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Cervical cancer, health beliefs, education, attitudes

INTRODUCTION

Cancers are increasing worldwide and are the 2nd most common cause of death. The 4th most common cancer in women is cervical cancer. Approximately 570,000 women in the world were diagnosed with cervical cancer in 2018 and approximately 311,000 women died due to this disease (World Health Organization, n.d). In Turkey, cervical cancer ranks 10th among female cancers (Özkan et al., 2023). The incidence of cervical cancer has more than halved since the mid-1970s as screening became more widespread. The incidence remained generally stable between 2015 and 2019, but varies by age, race and ethnicity (Siegel et al., 2023). Most cervical cancer is caused by the Human Papillomavirus. Most people are exposed to the virus at some point in their lives and are usually asymptomatic and recover spontaneously. In some women, however, cervical cancer develops (Centers of Disease Control and Prevention, n.d). The HPV vaccine provides 90% protection against cervical cancer and other HPV-related cancers and diseases. At the same time, screening to prevent cervical cancer can lead to early detection so that treatment can be more successful. However, half of those diagnosed with cervical cancer have never been screened (American Cancer Society, 2022). It is very important that family physicians and healthcare professionals, who have an important position in protecting the health of individuals, inform and guide patients about screening for early diagnosis and treatment. Our aim in this study was to determine the attitudes of women towards the diagnosis of cervical cancer and the factors affecting them, and to determine how their attitudes changed after they were given information about cervical cancer by a primary care physician.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study is an educational intervention study with a one-group pretest-posttest design. The population of the study consisted of 670 women aged 30-65 years registered in Tirebolu Family Medicine Center (FHC) numbered 28.15.002. With the help of the G*PowerVersion 3.1.7 program, a sample size of at least 54 patients was calculated to be representative of the population, based on a medium effect size ($d=0.50$) difference being clinically significant (Dawson-Sander & Trapp, 1994; Hulley et al., 2013). Data were obtained with a questionnaire including sociodemographic information and the "Attitude Scale for Early Diagnosis of Cervical Cancer". The scale suggests that relevant health behavior will occur if individuals perceive the disease as sensitivity for themselves, believe in the consequences related to the severity of the disease, are aware of both the benefits and barriers of screening, and have positive motivators to take action regarding screening. The scale includes nine items for the 'Perceived Sensitivity' subscale; eight items for the 'Perceived Severity' subscale; seven items for the 'Perceived Barriers' subscale; and six items for the 'Perceived Benefits' subscale (Özmen & Özsoy, 2009). The questionnaire and scale were administered to the participants face-to-face by the physician both before and after the training. For the training, the Ministry of Health's cervical cancer screening brochures for the public and Başkent University's "Is the elimination of cervical cancer in the world and in Turkey a dream or realizable?" resources were used (Akin & Topal, 2021). Participants were between the ages of 30-65, who applying to the family health center for any reason, had the cognitive ability to speak and understand Turkish, and agreed to participate in the study. Those who received training on cervical cancer screening or had a screening test in the last 3 months were not included in the study. Ethics committee approval was granted by Giresun Training and Research Hospital Clinical Research Ethics Committee with the decision number 27.02.2023/ 09 (KAEK no: 43). Study permission was obtained from Giresun Provincial Health Directorate (E-41544352-799-212127112).

Data were analyzed with IBM SPSS V23. Mann-Whitney U test was applied for non-normally distributed data between groups, and Independent two sample t-test for normally distributed data. Paired two-sample t-test was used for within group comparisons of normally distributed data and Wilcoxon test for non-normally distributed data. Results were presented as mean \pm SD and median (minimum-maximum) for quantitative, and frequency (percentage) for categorical data. Significance level was taken as $p<0.050$.

RESULTS

The mean age of the women who participated in the study was 45.73 ± 8.98 years. The majority of participants are housewives (72.7%) and have nuclear families (83.6%).

Although the rate of those who were aware of cervical cancer screening tests was quite high (96.4%), only 12.7% of the participants received education about cervical cancer.

The mean total score of the patients before the training was 100.76 ± 11.23 and the mean total score after the training was 102.47 ± 12.36 (Table 1).

Table 1

Descriptive statistics of scale scores

	Before		After		p
	Mean \pm SD	Median (min. - max.)	Mean \pm SD	Median (min. - max.)	
sensitivity	29,20 \pm 5,22	30,00 (17,00 - 41,00)	30,78 \pm 6,67	32,00 (8,00 - 44,00)	0,012
severity	27,09 \pm 4,85	27,00 (13,00 - 37,00)	26,38 \pm 6,00	26,00 (11,00 - 40,00)	0,101
barriers	21,00 \pm 4,11	22,00 (12,00 - 31,00)	21,45 \pm 4,51	21,00 (13,00 - 36,00)	0,346
benefits	23,27 \pm 3,09	23,00 (15,00 - 29,00)	23,84 \pm 3,93	24,00 (8,00 - 30,00)	0,065
Total	100,76 \pm 11,23	102,00 (72,00 - 123,00)	102,47 \pm 12,36	103,00 (60,00 - 133,00)	0,121

t: Paired two-sample t-test statistic, Z: Wilcoxon test statistic,

As a result of the comparison of sociodemographic data and perceived sensitivity scores, there was a difference in perceived sensitivity scores before and after the training for those with large families, non-smokers, those who did not have regular gynecological examinations, those who had no previous education and those who had no family history of cancer ($p < 0.05$).

When analyzed in terms of perceived severity scores, median perceived severity scores differed according to educational status ($p = 0.012$). The mean perceived severity scores of high school graduates, those with nuclear family structure, and those with no family history of cancer differed before and after the training ($p < 0.050$). There was no significant difference between the demographic data before and after the training in terms of barriers scores ($p > 0.05$).

When the perceived benefits scores were compared with demographic data, the mean perceived benefits score after the training differed according to family type ($p = 0.048$). While the median score of those living in large families was 26.00, the median score of those with nuclear family structure was 24.00. The median scores after education differed according to the status of regular gynecological examination ($p = 0.03$). There was no significant difference between and within demographic characteristics in the comparison of total scale scores ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

In this study, the total scale score of the patients before the training was above the average and the total scale score increased after the training. In the study conducted by Shojaeizadeh (2011), there was a significant increase in scale scores after training. Women with positive attitudes and high level of knowledge are more likely to show the necessary behavior (Enyan et al., 2022). In our study, the majority of women accepted the screening test after the training and stated that they would go to have the test, which aligns with the study conducted in Turkey (Bal & Şahiner, 2020).

One study shows that women whose family physicians recommend a pap-smear test are about 3 times more likely to have one than those who do not. The most important barriers to screening include not going to the doctor, lack of advice and lack of information (Ghazi et al., 2023).

In our study, although perceived sensitivity scores were high before the training, a significant difference was observed after training ($p < 0.05$). Previous studies support this finding (Abdelmonsef Ahmed et al., 2023.; Logaraj, 2023). Post-training sensitivity is affected by educational level, family history of cancer and other sociodemographic characteristics. It has been observed that women with low educational level have high sensitivity to cancer. This coincides with the study by Aldohaian et al. (2019).

In our study, perceived severity scores decreased after the training. This suggests that the presence of a screening test for cervical cancer, which is a serious disease, may have led to a decrease in its severity by providing psychological relief (Mardani et al., 2024).

It is desirable to decrease perceived barriers and increase perceived benefits, but perceived barriers did not always decrease significantly in most studies. In our study, the fact that the pre-training barrier scores were at a moderate level and did not decrease after the training, although we expected it to decrease after the training, is in line with the studies conducted by Ampofo (2020), Samami (2021), and their colleagues. This may be due to cultural or socioeconomic factors that cannot be easily changed by education.

CONCLUSION

Demographic factors such as education level, family type, smoking status and family or family history of cancer are related to the impact of education. Health care providers should be aware of barriers to screening. An education program for cervical cancer screening should include cultural knowledge and communication skills. Health workers should provide opportunities for patients to receive adequate information and opportunities to provide women with screening tests. Since primary care is easily accessible to patients, health workers should see that they can provide the best service that patients can get from primary care and that patients are open to education and referral. It should not be ignored that with education, patients' awareness will increase and participation rates in screening will also increase.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

No conflict of interest was declared by the authors.

REFERENCES

- Abdelmonsef Ahmed, H. A., Ibrahim Yassin, S. Y., Mohamed Ahmed, M. S., & Yousof Ali, H. Z. (2023). Application of Health Belief Model about cervical cancer screening among female officer employees in Kafr-El Sheikh University, Egypt. *JPMA. The Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*, 73(4), 67–7. <https://doi.org/10.47391/JPMA.EGY-S4-15>
- Akın, A., & Topal, E. (2021). *Dünyada ve Türkiye’de rahim ağzı kanserlerinin yok edilmesi bir hayal mi yoksa gerçekleştirilebilir mi?* Halk Sağlığı Okulu. <https://www.halksagligiokulu.org/Kitap/DownloadEBook/31e5011b-7a12-5c73-5986-3a02f233ac16>
- Aldohaian, A. I., Alshammari, S. A., & Arafah, D. M. (2019). Using the health belief model to assess beliefs and behaviors regarding cervical cancer screening among Saudi women: A cross-sectional observational study. *BMC Women’s Health*, 19, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-018-0701-2>
- American Cancer Society. (2022). *Cancer Facts & Figures*. <https://www.cancer.org/content/dam/cancer-org/research/cancer-facts-and-statistics/annual-cancer-facts-and-figures/2022/2022-cancer-facts-and-figures>
- Ampofo, A. G., Adumatta, A. D., Owusu, E., & Awuviry-Newton, K. (2020). A cross-sectional study of barriers to cervical cancer screening uptake in Ghana: An application of the health belief model. *PloS One*, 15(4), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231459>
- Bal, M. D., & Şahiner, N. C. (2020). The effect of health belief model-based training on cervical cancer screening behaviors. *Clinical and Experimental Health Sciences*, 10(3), 223–227. <https://doi.org/10.33808/clinexphealthsci.733948>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). (n.d.). *What are the risk factors for cervical cancer?* https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/cervical/basic_info/risk_factors.htm
- Dawson-Sanders, B., & Trapp, R. (1994). *Basic and Clinical Biostatistics*. Prentice Hall.

Enyan, N. I. E., Davies, A. E., Opoku-Danso, R., Annor, F., & Obiri-Yeboah, D. (2022). Correlates of cervical cancer screening participation, intention and self-efficacy among Muslim women in southern Ghana. *BMC Women's Health*, 22(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-022-01803-0>

Ghazi, A. A., Alturkistani, H. M., Alturkistani Jr, A. M., Alhajuj, H. Y., Alaidarous, A. A., Alturkistani Sr, H., & Alhajuj, H. (2023). Cervical cancer screening barriers among citizens of Jeddah. *Cureus*, 15(12), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.50797>

Hulley, S. B., Cummings, S. R., Browner, W. S., Grady, D. G., & Newman, T. B. (2013). *Designing Clinical Research: An Epidemiologic Approach* (2nd ed.). Lippincott.

Logaraj, M. (2023). The effect of the health belief model education for cervical cancer prevention, screening promotion among rural women in Chengalpattu district, Tamil Nadu (HBMECC). *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 12(1), 166–173. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_1133_22

Mardani, F., Vázquez, N. P., Rajendrakumar, J., & Saadati, S. M. (2024). Evaluating the efficacy of a multifaceted health behavior training program on psychological distress. *KMAN Counseling & Psychology Nexus*, 2(1), 34–41. <https://doi.org/10.61838/kman.psynexus.2.1.6>

Özkan, N. T., Çöteli, S. A. D., Öz, M., Yalçın, I., Aslan, K., Akilli, H., & Ayhan, A. (2023). #563 Cervical cancer burden of Türkiye in spite of a nation-based cervical cancer screening program. *International Journal of Gynecological Cancer*, 33(3), 80–81.

Özmen, D., & Özsoy, S. (2009). Developing an attitude scale for early diagnosis of cervical cancer with health belief model approach. *Ege Üniversitesi Hemşirelik Yüksek Okulu Dergisi*, 25(1), 51–69.

Samami, E., Seyedi-Andi, S. J., Bayat, B., Shojaeizadeh, D., & Tori, N. A. (2021). The effect of educational intervention based on the health belief model on knowledge, attitude, and function of women about Pap smear test at Iranian health centers: A randomized controlled clinical trial. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 10(1), 22–28. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_33_20

Shojaeizadeh, D., Hashemi, S. Z., Moeini, B., & Poorolajal, J. (2011). The effect of educational program on increasing cervical cancer screening behavior among women in Hamadan, Iran: Applying health belief model. *Journal of Research in Health Sciences*, 11(1), 20–25.

Siegel, R. L., Miller, K. D., Wagle, N. S., & Jemal, A. (2023). Cancer statistics. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*, 73(1), 17–48.

World Health Organization. (n.d.). *Health topics / Cervical cancer*. https://www.who.int/health-topics/cervical-cancer#tab=tab_1

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